

A Hybrid Early Warning System Based on IoT and Machine Learning for Heart Disease Prediction

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Abstract

The rapid development of the Internet of Things (IoT), enabled by the integration of sensors, embedded electronics, and networked software, has created new opportunities for real-time health monitoring applications. In the medical domain, IoT-based systems have gained significant attention for their ability to continuously acquire and transmit physiological parameters. This paper proposes an IoT-enabled early warning system for monitoring cardiac activity and generating alerts when abnormal heart conditions are detected. The proposed system is designed to support nursing staff by automatically notifying responsible personnel through a mobile application in the event of abnormal heart rate patterns. Data collected from multi-sensor physiological measurements are analyzed using several machine learning classification techniques to identify potential cardiac disorders. Experimental results indicate that the decision tree classifier achieves the highest accuracy of 97.08% in distinguishing abnormal cardiac conditions. Unlike existing IoT-based heart monitoring solutions, the proposed model integrates multi-sensor data acquisition, real-time GPS-based emergency tracking, and a multi-model machine learning evaluation framework validated using both UCI benchmark datasets and real sensor measurements. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system for accurate early detection of cardiac abnormalities in clinical monitoring environments.

Keywords: IoT; Arduino; Decision Tree; Warning System; Heart Disease.

1. Introduction

The pumping action of the heart generates cyclic systolic and diastolic pressures that are fundamental indicators of cardiovascular health. Systolic pressure occurs during ventricular contraction, when blood is ejected from the heart, whereas diastolic pressure corresponds to the relaxation phase between contractions, during which the heart chambers fill with blood. The frequency of these cycles is expressed as the heart rate (pulse rate). Continuous monitoring of these physiological parameters is essential for the early detection and management of cardiovascular disorders.

Recent advances in sensor technology and the Internet of Things (IoT) have enabled real-time acquisition and remote monitoring of vital signs. Physiological sensors can detect blood pressure, heart rate, and body temperature and transmit the acquired data to

embedded platforms for electronic processing and analysis. These measurements represent primary indicators for tracking cardiac health and identifying abnormal conditions at an early stage.

In this study, an IoT-based health monitoring system is proposed that integrates physiological sensing, cloud connectivity, and intelligent data analysis. The system couples' biomedical sensors with an Arduino-based embedded platform, which continuously monitors systolic pressure, diastolic pressure, and pulse rate. The collected data are transmitted to a cloud server for further processing and analysis. In cases where abnormal heart rate patterns are detected, an alert message is automatically delivered to a mobile device. Additionally, a Global Positioning System (GPS) module is incorporated to identify the real-time location of the patient, enabling rapid emergency response.

To enhance diagnostic accuracy, several machine learning (ML) techniques including k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, and Logistic Regression are employed to analyze the acquired physiological data. The training dataset is obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Repository, while experimental validation is performed using real-time data collected from IoT sensors across different age groups. Among the evaluated models, the Decision Tree classifier achieved the highest prediction accuracy of 97.08%, demonstrating its effectiveness in handling both numerical and categorical medical data. Accurate classification is critical for early detection of potential cardiac events, where timely intervention can significantly reduce health risks.

Although several IoT-based cardiac monitoring systems have been reported in the literature, many treat physiological sensing and machine learning-based prediction as independent components. The novelty of this work lies in the development of a unified hybrid early-warning system that seamlessly integrates continuous physiological monitoring, intelligent prediction, and real-time emergency alerting within a single deployable architecture. By combining IoT-based sensing, multi-model machine learning analysis, cloud computing, and GSM-based alerting with GPS localization, the proposed system provides a comprehensive and practical solution for real-time heart health monitoring and early warning of cardiac abnormalities

2. Literature Review

One of the important applications outlined by the IoT is a continuous heart disease monitoring system. Combining powerful expert systems with vast amounts of medical data on cardiac problems may help achieve this objective. Considering this, the authors developed a system that helps patients obtain timely medical attention by exploiting the Internet of Things. By putting a finger on a pulse sensor, this method determines the user's heartbeat. This system has a segment that continuously collects heartbeat data and a section that calculates heartbeat. In this strategy, we present a technique for automatically reacting to a patient's pulse while remotely monitoring it [1]. Heart attack prognosis is a possible tool. The study uses IOT to communicate with the individual, multiple

regressions to predict heart attacks, cloud platforms, and IOT devices to remind the individual of his risk of suffering a heart attack. The created framework could upload the collected data to a server that regularly gets updates [2]. The model must be trained in any medical expert system using a sophisticated and effective method. The article suggests the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) algorithm as a viable tactic in keeping with this concept. RNN is used in the proposed method to do heart disease diagnoses. To detect ailments, an IoT-Based Heart Disease Detection System uses a neural network. After RNN a neural network operation for illness diagnosis is performed based on comparisons with the training dataset [3].

Smartphones are essential to the Internet of Things. Considering this, the paper proposes a heart rate detection technique using an Android smartphone, an Arduino microcontroller, and a pulse sensor. Its foundation is the notion of using a light source and detector to track alterations in blood volume inside of our bodies. The results demonstrate that the user's heart rate is higher under unusual conditions than it is under typical conditions. The smartphone monitor will display the findings if the pulse sensor detects a dangerous heart rate scenario, and an automated warning sound will be produced [4]. Heart problems are especially common among the elderly population. A system was created utilizing machine learning techniques including Naive Bayes, XGBoost gradient classifiers, decision trees, and support vector machines (SVM). The combined Cleveland and Stalog dataset are used in the proposal. Thirteen diagnostic criteria and five environmental variables are looked at [5]. To identify significant independent predictors relating to the outcome of heart failure versus chronic ischemic heart disease, the authors used a combination of biochemical parameters in a logistic regression-based model that, on average, would excellently discriminate the outcome of heart failure versus chronic ischemic heart disease in the elderly population. [6]. The article's goal was to determine if substantial left main stenosis could be predicted using a range of clinical, laboratory, and non-invasive test data as well as information on common cardiac disorders. Between April 2010 and March 2019, all adult patients in Ontario, Canada, who had stress testing before elective coronary angiography for stable ischemic heart disease were included [7].

Machine learning is one of the most well-liked categories for classification. In the proposed study, the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) approach, a supervised machine learning technique, is used to predict heart disease and extract decision rules to elucidate correlations between input and output variables. The re-search's conclusions also list the heart disease risk factors in order of relevance [8]. The most recent data on PCI, hybrid coronary revascularization (HCR), and off-pump coronary artery bypass grafting (OPCAB) performance, indications, advantages, and limitations were reviewed. A novel decision tree that incorporates the most recent developments in minimally invasive revascularization techniques is offered to optimize the proper administration of treatment for each specific patient's demands. This data served as the basis for this decision tree, together with the knowledge discovered during Heart Team conversations [9]. Further investigation into various methodologies leads to a proposal that uses

OpenCL to explore how different parallelization and optimization tactics may be utilized to speed up the DCT-KNN algorithm on the FPGA parallel computing platform. According to the experimental findings, the DCT-KNN algorithm performs extremely well on the FPGA platform when compared to the conventional single-core CPU-based implementation [10]. Extreme effectiveness is a challenging feat, but the study found that the RF approach, using a heart disease dataset obtained from Kaggle three-classification based on k-nearest neighbour (KNN), decision tree (DT), and random forests (RF) algorithms, achieved 100% accuracy as well as 100% sensitivity and specificity. As a result, we discovered that a rather straightforward supervised machine learning technique may be used to predict cardiac illness quite accurately and with a large amount of potential utility [11]. The support vector machine (SVM) technique and a modified particle swarm optimization model are used in this work to build a hybrid model for the categorization of heart and liver data. The UCI machine learning library is where the data sets are obtained. Classification accuracy, error, correctness, recall, and F1 score are used to calculate the results [12]. Prior studies relied on either cloud-based sensing or ML-only prediction. Our work uniquely couples real-time data from efficient sensors with on-device preprocessing and a GPS-enabled alert delivery system integrated with ML prediction.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Creation of a hybrid IoT–ML early warning system that combines temperature, blood pressure, and pulse monitoring into a single embedded platform.
- GPS-based location identification and real-time crisis alerts for prompt medical attention.
- Mapping and validating real sensor measurements with the UCI Heart Disease dataset.
- A comparative ML analysis (LR, DT, KNN, SVM) using both real sensor data and benchmark datasets, showing Decision Tree achieves superior performance.
- A complete hardware–software workflow suitable for deployment in nursing homes and small clinical centres.

3. Methodology

3.1 Hardware & Software Setup

The proposed system architecture is divided into two main components: the IoT-based sensing process and the machine learning–based classification process, as illustrated in Figure 1. The overall model, shown in Figure 2, integrates both hardware and software components to detect abnormalities in a patient’s heart rate, blood pressure, and body temperature within a hospital environment. When abnormal physiological conditions are detected, an alert message is automatically sent to the concerned nursing staff. Simultaneously, the patient’s location is identified using GPS latitude and longitude coordinates, enabling prompt medical intervention. This system allows a single nurse to monitor multiple patients concurrently, thereby improving efficiency and response time.

The hardware setup consists of an Arduino Uno microcontroller, pulse sensor, blood pressure sensor, temperature sensor, GSM module, and GPS sensor. The Arduino Uno serves as the central processing unit of the system, interfacing with the sensors through its analog input ports. The sensors are placed in contact with the patient to continuously acquire physiological parameters. The measured pulse rate, blood pressure, and temperature data are transmitted to the server and displayed locally on an LCD screen.

In the event of abnormal readings, an alarm mechanism is triggered, indicated by a blinking red LED. Additionally, a text message containing the patient’s vital information and GPS-based location coordinates is sent to the designated medical personnel via the GSM module. This integrated alerting mechanism ensures rapid response and enhances patient safety.

Arduino coding is based on the C language. From this data we have applied a machine learning algorithm to predict heart diseases.

The proposed system follows a five-stage workflow:

1. Physiological Sensing: Pulse, blood pressure, and temperature sensors continuously acquire vital signals.
2. Microcontroller Processing: The Arduino Uno does threshold-based anomaly detection and digitizes sensor outputs.
3. Cloud Communication: The GSM module uses the HTTP/REST API to upload data packets including timestamp, vitals, and device ID to a cloud server.
4. Prediction Layer: Heart disease risk is categorized by the cloud/PC-based ML engine using UCI features that are in line with actual sensor data.
5. Emergency Alerting: The device sends a real-time SMS alert with GPS information to the designated medical attendant when it detects aberrant values.

Figure 1. Process Flow Diagram

Figure 2. Hardware architecture

3.2 Comparative study of Machine Learning approaches

The data collected from the IoT device, is analysed using four different Machine Learning based classification approaches as stated below:

3.2.1 Logistic Regression

It is frequently employed to calculate the likelihood that a given instance belongs to a specific class. The model predicts that the instance belongs to that class if the estimated probability is more than 50%; otherwise, it predicts that it does not. It is a binary classifier as a result [6, 14]. The relationship depicted below illustrates how the linear function is effectively used as an input to another function, such as g , in logistic regression:

$$h_{\theta}(x) = g(\theta_{Tx}) \text{ where } 0 \leq h_{\theta} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

The logistic or sigmoid function, denoted by the letter g , may be expressed as follows:

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \text{ where } z = \theta_{Tx} \quad (2)$$

3.2.2 Decision Tree

They are adaptable Machine Learning algorithms that can carry out tasks requiring classification, regression, and even multiple outputs. Complex datasets can be fitted by them [15]. Figure 3 describes the process flow of Decision Tree method.

Figure 3. Decision Tree architecture

3.2.3 KNN (K Nearest Neighbors)

Such a technique is K-Nearest Neighbours (kNN), which although being straight forward, nonetheless works rather well for big training sets. It is based solely on the fundamental principle of every prediction, which holds that observations with similar features will often provide outputs that are similar. The plurality or mean of an observation's k "Nearest Neighbours" in the training set, which is frequently weighted, is used by Nearest Neighbour approaches to predict the value of a new observation. Any observation, given an infinite amount of data, will have many "neighbours" that are arbitrarily close with respect to all measured characteristics, and the variability of their results will provide the most accurate prediction possible, barring a model that is entirely and accurately specified [16].

3.2.4 SVM (Support Vector Machine)

Finding a hyperplane in an N-dimensional space (N is the number of features) that clearly classifies the data points is the goal of the SVM. There are a variety of different hyperplanes that might be used to split the two classes of data points. Finding a plane with the largest margin that is, the largest space between data points for both classes is the goal. Maximising the margin distance adds some support, increasing the confidence with which future data points may be categorized [17].

3.2.4.1 Variables Description

We have considered the following data variables as applicable for our proposed system.

Age – Age of the subject

Sex – Gender of the subject

cp – Type of chest discomfort

trestbps - Subject's resting heart rate

pulse – Subject's pulse rate

thalach - Subject's attainment of the highest heart rate

exang - Angina brought on by exercise

3.2.4.2 Classification Algorithm

We have seen through our study of various literatures that Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN and SVM are the most popular classification algorithms used in different studies. Hence, we carried out a comparative analysis of the four algorithms. The detailed process is as follows:

- a. Data Import from CSV File
- b. Arrangement of the classes
- c. Choosing undesirable columns
- d. Delete unnecessary columns
- e. Split the data into Train and Test datasets.
- f. Modelling (Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN and SVM)

g. Analyzing prophecies

4. Results and Discussion

The total hardware set up has been shown in the above figures (Figure 4 until Figure 9). Temperature, pulse sensor and blood pressure sensor relate to analog input of the Arduino uno. The GSM module relates to transmitter, receiver and ground pin. The vcc pin of the GSM module is connected to the 5-volt supply, and the transmitter pin of the GPS module is connected to one of the digital pins. When the temperature, pulse and blood pressure exceed normal rated value the LED will blink, value is displayed in the LCD screen, and the text message is sent to the mobile number which has been mentioned in the coding, and the position coordinate of the actor is mentioned in the text message. To correctly predict heart disease probability, based on information gathered from five factors utilizing IoT-based sensors, the Decision Tree classification technique for identifying heart diseases achieved an accuracy of 97.08%. Results obtained from accuracy test are shown in Table 1.

Figure 4. Patient's location displayed on LCD

Figure 5. SMS sending using GSM module

Figure 6. Location data send to specified mobile number

Figure 7. Patient's information as recorded on Blood Pressure sensor

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Your heart Beat is : 69
Your heart Beat is : 69
Your heart Beat is : 71
Your heart Beat is : 71
Your heart Beat is : 71
Your heart Beat is : 72
Your heart Beat is : 72
Your heart Beat is : 74
Your heart Beat is : 75
Your heart Beat is : 75
Your heart Beat is : 76
Your heart Beat is : 77
Your heart Beat is : 79
Your heart Beat is : 82
Your heart Beat is : 82
Your heart Beat is : 59
Your heart Beat is : 64
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Figure 8. Continuous pulse rate display

Figure 9. Blood pressure sensor module

Table 1. Classification Algorithm accuracy chart

	Accuracy on Training data	Accuracy on Test data
Logistic Regression	80.20%	73.70%
Decision Tree	99%	97.08%
KNN	95.8%	92.86%
SVM	71.27%	66.23%

A sample set of real-time physiological values obtained via the IoT hardware module and the accompanying machine-learning predictions produced by the system are shown in Table 2. Under typical monitoring conditions, each user's body temperature, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and pulse rate were recorded. The trained classifier then evaluated these numbers to determine whether the person displayed normal or at-risk traits. Users 1, 3, and 5 are classified as "Normal" by the model due to their near-normal temperature, stable blood pressure, and mild pulse rates.

The table illustrates how the IoT-based sensor data and the ML classifier collaborate to differentiate between normal and potentially dangerous physiological conditions, validating the usefulness of the suggested early-warning system. In contrast, Users 2 and 4 exhibit elevated pulse and blood pressure values along with higher temperature in the case of User 2, which align with typical indicators of cardiovascular strain. As a result, the ML model correctly labels them as "At-risk." Pulse and blood pressure readings from medical-grade devices showed acceptable sensor accuracy for early-warning use cases, with deviations staying within ± 3 units.

The suggested solution integrates comparative machine learning categorization, GPS-enabled patient localization, real-time distress signaling, and continuous vital sign monitoring into a single deployable architecture. The operational difficulties encountered in nursing homes, where a single nurse must concurrently oversee several patients, are immediately addressed by this integration.

Table 2. Sample IoT Sensor Readings from Real Users

User	Pulse (bpm)	BP Systolic	BP Diastolic	Temp (°C)	ML Prediction	Status
1	78	122	82	36.9	0	Normal
2	104	148	96	38.1	1	At-risk
3	65	118	79	36.5	0	Normal
4	111	160	102	37.8	1	At-risk
5	89	135	90	37	0	Normal

5. Conclusion

The term "IoT" refers to both a system of interconnected devices as well as the technology that enables such communication. It plays a significant role in modern medical practice. IoT may be used to anticipate and identify heart disease. This study aims to predict heart illness using an IoT platform. UCI The suggested system receives data from the Machine Learning Repository as input. The data from the IoT module, which was created to gather data on the temperature, blood pressure, and pulse rates of several people across a range of age groups, was used to evaluate the classification model based on the Decision Tree method. If any irregularity is found by the sensors while considering the patients equipped with the suggested system, an instant distress alert with Geo positional information will be sent to the medical attendant. Through precise early prediction, the model will be able to prevent people from developing heart disease. The efficacy of our suggested module is demonstrated by the accuracy of 97.08%.

In our future work, we will increase the sensor module and find an even more effective categorization mechanism in our next study. Despite the system's great accuracy using Decision Trees, there are still issues with sensor diversity and dataset size. Future research will concentrate on integrating ECG/SPO2 sensors, growing the real-world dataset, and using lightweight deep-learning models for on-device prediction, like 1D-CNN and LSTM. For extensive clinical integration, the system can potentially be expanded to hospital information systems.

Conflict of Interests

The authors affirm there are no competing financial interests or organizational influences affecting this work.

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Cite this article as: Chakraborty S., Mukherjee T. A Hybrid Early Warning System Based on IoT and Machine Learning for Heart Disease Prediction, *Journal of Integrated Engineering and Applied Sciences*. 2025; 3(2); 257-269.